

GIRL-CHILD EDUCATION: A CRITICAL ISSUE FOR NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

Educate a woman and you have successfully educated a nation goes the saying; thus, girl-child education has become a contemporary issue to nations in the world because girls/women are usually discriminated against in all spheres of life including education. It is on this thrust that this paper examined the girl-child marginalization and with unequal access to education in comparism to her male counterpart. The study reveals that cultural practices serve as hindrance to girl-child education and that inaccessibility of the girl-child to education makes her vulnerable to diseases such as HIV/AIDS, early marriage, denial of rights and child labour. The study concluded on the note that if girl-child education is fostered, she will be self-reliant, adequately socialize and well empowered to contribute meaningfully to her community as well as having the coping skills to problems solving to an appreciable extent. The study, therefore, recommends that education should be made accessible to the girl-child at all levels and awareness programs should be floated and fostered to redeem the image of the girl-child to make the world a better place for her to live in

BACKGROUND

Illiteracy has been regarded as an enemy and evil which keep people in darkness, bound to their traditions and superstitions; makes people resistant to change and new ideas and isolated from progress, thus unaware and incapable of meeting the demands of their changing environment and ever progressing world. Nasution in Omolewa (1985)

Girl-child education is a matter of concern for nations in the world. Girl-children are discriminated against thereby making it difficult for them to exercise their rights; they are victims of various traditional/cultural practices, they suffer degradation, they are objects of poverty, their faces are only to be seen but their voices not to be heard, they are seen as being sub-servient to their male counterparts; they are the inferior set, their place is in the kitchen. A lot of negative thoughts and actions are expressed on the girl-child. To set the girl-child free from all these negative hold, there is need for her sound education. Giving her education will give her sound mind to reason, to liberate herself from poverty, and develop herself as well as the nation in which she lives. With education, the girl child can become a self-sufficient adult who has more decision and control over her life. Jatau in Esomonu (1999) believes that the burden of nation building rests much on women. She goes on "we need women to create a blissful home, have well-educated and well-behaved children.... it is after these that the task of nation building can be a success". This will start from the education of the girl-child. The importance of educating the girl-child is further brought to the fore by Abacha (1997) while stating his view to support the fact that development has to be participatory and sustainable. He believed that:

Progress is only feasible if we create a Nigeria made up of a united people with a united purpose... our nation needs men and women who are bold, and imaginative, dedicated and committed, people who put honour, service and patriotism above everything else. These men and women are not only needed in politics, they are also needed in business, in our traditional institutions, youth organizations, in academics and other professions".

The indication from the above is that society should stop looking down on women and they should be seen as first class citizen and not rated as second-class citizens. Educating the girl-child (who transforms later into a woman) will empower her to be strong and resourceful in such a way that she is able to contribute maximally to the sustenance and development of the society in which she lives. According to Alkali (2000), if all limiting barriers against women are removed, "women can lead, lead to the battle, if necessary fight for her society and win for her people". Educating a girl child therefore will bring about self-awareness, increased self assertiveness in the society, raising the consciousness of women to encourage their participation in national development (Awe, 1992).

It is therefore important that particular and close attention to paid to the education of the girl-child. Finding the right solution to the issue of girl-child education will not only move the girl-child forward but pushes the nation to a greater height. Considering the virtues embedded in the issue of girl child education, the issue should be rated very high.

The Instructional Manual on the Advancement of Nigerian Women and the Role of National and International Agencies (1996) states that to promote the advancement of Nigerian women, it is important that individuals, groups, community and government at all levels have a duty to take action in the following areas:

- ❖ Reducing the rate of poverty among women
- ❖ Making sure that girls and women have equal opportunities for training and education as boys and men.
- ❖ Making sure that girls and women have adequate opportunities for proper health care.
- ❖ Preventing all kinds of violence against women and girls
- ❖ Protecting the best interest and rights of the girl-child.

When these actions are taken, the rights of the girl-child will be fully restored through her being educated. Who is a girl-child?

For the purpose of this paper, a girl-child shall be taken for female children between the ages of 6 and 15. Those who are expected to have free access to the free Federal Government provided Universal Basic Education.

Issues on Girl-Child Education

Kofi Annan (2001) says:

“No development strategy is better than one that involves women as central players. It has immediate benefits for nutrition, health, savings and re-investment at the family, community and ultimately, country level. In order words, educating girls is a social development policy that works. It is a long-term investment that yields on exceptionally high return.

The above statement represents a call for girl-child education. It is however, discovered that girl-child education is not easy to come by as it is usually proclaimed as many impediments stand in the way of the girl-child. The rights of the girl-children are always denied them and this denial leads to lack of access to education. Inaccessibility to education thus results in child labour, which deprives the girl-child of her childhood potentials, dignity and joy. The resultant effect is poverty and the only key to ending poverty among women-folk, as a whole is education of the girl-child because as the saying goes “catch them young” for the young girl-child will grow to full woman in later years.

Rights of the girl-child

Every individual in the society is entitled to some rights as citizens of that particular society. The same is true of the girl-child. She is entitled to a lot of human rights but because she is regarded as being weak she is vulnerable to the violations of these rights. Like any other person in the society, she likewise requires the right to enjoy and exercise these rights. Some of the rights of the girl-child as stated by The People’s Movement for Human Rights Education (www.humanrights/girledu...) include the following:

- Right to freedom from discrimination based on gender, age, race, colour, language, ethnicity or the status of the girl-child’s parents.
- Right to a standard of living adequate for a child’s intellectual, physical, moral and spiritual development.
- Right to a safe and healthy environment
- Right to equal access to food and nutrition.
- Right to freedom from cultural practices, customs and traditions harmful to the girl-child including female genital mutilation.
- Right to education- free and compulsory primary education and freedom from all types of discrimination at all levels of education.

Linked with the above rights is the right to information about health, sexuality and reproduction, protection form physical and mental abuse.

It is pertinent to note that the girl-child can only claim these rights and exercise them if she understands what they mean and their implications upon her livelihood and dignity. The girl-child should therefore be made to know that education is empowerment and when she is empowered, she can fight for her rights and exercise such. Education of the girl-child therefore must be seen as a priority in the educational process of any nation. This calls for bridging the existing gender gap in education before any enduring success can be recorded. Lack of education of the girl-child denies her the knowledge and skills needed to advance her status and so she remains below the poverty level, wasting away in abject poverty worsened by illnesses and diseases. When a girl-child is educated, she is able to realize her full potentials, think, question and judge independently, develop civic sense, learn to respect, her fellow human beings and be a good citizen (Girl-child campaign, government of India-www.read-org/publication – 16-10-07).

To enable the girl-child enjoy the rights stated above, the United Nations, Fourth World Conference on Women, Beijing (1995) formulated some strategic objectives which include the following:

- Elimination of all forms of discrimination against the girl-child
- Elimination of negative cultural practices and attitudes against girls.
- Promotion and protection of the rights of the girl-child and promotion of awareness of her needs and potentials.
- Elimination of discrimination against girls in education and skills.
- Elimination of discrimination against girls in health and nutrition.
- Promotion of the girl-child's awareness of and participation in social, economic and political life. (www.un.org/womanwatch/daw.beijing/ platform/girl.html accessed – 17-10-07).

If these strategic objectives are followed to the letter, this will result in awareness of the girl-child and she will be able to reach out for that which belongs to her after being exposed to a measure of education. Educating a girl-child therefore will free her from poverty, illness, diseases and malnutrition.

Hindrances to Girl-Child Education

According to UNESCO (2003) as quoted by Indabawa (2004), females constitute more than 50% of the World's active population. Despite the fact that they face a number of inequitable difficulties that limit their potentials in promoting personal and collective development, they are still known to make great contributions towards national development. Some of the factors hindering the education of the girl-child as listed by Indabawa (2004) include the following:

1. Early marriage: Girl-children are given off in marriage between the ages of ten and fourteen limiting their chances of being formally educated and with no provision for non-formal education for them in later life.
2. Hawking Practices: Girl-Children are mostly found in these practices. The male-child education is much more valued than that of the girl-child so she is to help generate income to supplement the efforts of the parents. This robs her of access to education. To worsen matters, in the process of hawking she comes across unwanted pregnancy, which if care is not taken, leaves her suffering for her lifetime.
3. The poverty level of families: most families are very poor and so they have to make a choice between girl-child's education and their male ones. Traditionally, since male-children are more valued, parents mostly resorted to making their choices to favour the education of the male child leaving the girl-child impoverished.
4. Societal attitude to girl-child: The girl-child is a weaker vessel, her place is in the kitchen, and she will use her education to benefit her husband, so why bother to send her to school? The societal attitude toward the girl-child is not in support of her education and so this makes her education to be described as dwindling as and less than equal to that of their male counterpart (Indabawa, 1998, Obanya, 2003).
5. Low Self-Concept: Another hindering factor is the girl-child's low self-concept. She sees herself as not being able to cope with the challenges of modern learning, so she begins to find excuses, like, that after schooling. There are no job opportunities so; it would be better for her to stay out of the reach of education. Solutions must be sought to these and other impediments because girl-child education is a must if the nation is to make any appreciable progress.

The Way Forward

When a girl child is educated, not only the family but also the whole nation is being educated. This is so because of her reproductive tendency and the influence she exerts on the children as the first teacher. An illiterate mother is likely to breed illiterate children while literate mothers are likely to breed enlightened children. To meet the needs of the society and to have poverty reduced, education of the girl-child must be made viable in the light of the fact that education is the key to personal as well as national development (Lassa, 1996). So gender equity in education should be promoted so as to create a healthy educated and productive human base. Ukeje (2000) states that education is so powerful that it can heal, kill, it can build up or tear apart; it can lift up or impoverish. Education is important in building up a sound individual with sound health for the price of illiteracy is poverty and poverty is intricately linked with health. The more a child suffers from poverty, the more prone the child is to illness, disease and malnutrition and the more the girl and parents are susceptible to health problems, their abilities to earn an income to survive is diminished. This has been regarded as a vicious and unmerciful cycle (Stop Child Poverty 2002).

To end this cycle, the girl-child must be educated. Girl-children who are not educated cannot have adequate access to information on how to prevent diseases and this unenlightened tendency will prevent them from having access to medical treatment and care produced in the hospitals. The above highlighted hindrances constitute challenges to girl-child education and with these challenges in mind, the people must be sensitized to the community and social benefits of educating girls. Parents especially women, should be given opportunities for income generating activities by both the various NGOs and governmental agencies to make funds available for the education of the girl-child.

World Universal School Community (WUSC,2002) suggests the use of holistic multi-level participatory approach. This approach calls for collaboration of local partners and parents in formulating educational policies and management of education. The argument is that when there is community participation in the planning and management of education, those who had hitherto being gender biased would see the need for the education of the girl-child and will work towards such. With the empowerment of parents through their participation in education matters, they are more likely to send and keep their girl-children in school and this will result in what WUSC (2002) termed "higher girl-child retention rates and locally appropriate sustainable girl-friendly education systems".

When the girl-child or children generally are not educated, it results into child-labour and quoting Jose Maria Sumpisa on World Day Against Child Labour (2007), that "the true winning strategy against child labour is to reduce poverty in rural area...", this strategy is only found in no other thing but in education. Child labour is that work that deprives children of their childhood, their potential, dignity and which is harmful to their physical and mental development (ILO-IPEC 2002 in Stop Child Poverty-Child Labour 2002).

It can be said that child labour interferes with schooling by depriving children of opportunity to attend school and sometimes obliging them to leave school prematurely. Child labour makes children miss out in the childhood opportunities which most children enjoy and thus leading to the child not receiving basic education. Education should therefore be seen as a corner stone of a solid foundation to break free from the cycle of poverty. The long-term solution to the problem of child labour as recommended by UNICEF (2002) is that of the child (in this case girl-child) being afforded the opportunities or access to education and a healthy childhood.

It is therefore, pertinent for the girl-child to be educated to be liberated from the hold of child-labour as well as the scourge of HIV/AIDS and other social ills as faced by the girl-child.

When a girl child is educated, her knowledge base is expanded, she is able to understand and undertake socio-economic, cultural and political transformations necessary to achieve development. Education of the girl-child is positively related to her living standard and the only effective scheme to alleviate poverty is to expand the educational opportunities available to the girl child. The type of education being prescribed for the girl-child is one that will make her self-reliant (National Policy on Education 2004). With education, a girl child is made aware of her condition and she is empowered to seek solutions to her problems. When she is educated, she is empowered to fight against powerful social structures, cultural traditional practices and attitudes that are retarding progress in the society.

Educating a girl child will therefore help her socialize, reproduce knowledge and even lead her towards the production of new knowledge. This will lead her to alter the way she perceives of herself in the society and help her to cope with living in the society. Owing to this importance of education, it should not be seen as an exclusive reserve for the male-children. The right to education should be for all. In education lies communal spirit, in that it helps people to respect the views of others by promoting understanding, tolerance and friendship among the people of a community, races and nations (Anyanwu, 1992). To bring about all these positive things that could result from being educated, the girl-child must not be excluded.

The World Declaration on Education for All (EFA) (1990) emphasizes that learning opportunity shall be expanded for all so that every individual will participate in the process of nation building. To include everybody in the process of education therefore, suitable programmes should be provided according to the needs of the people and included in the Curriculum. When the girl-child is educated, she is able to further the case of social justice and is tolerant socially, politically and emotionally. For education to be effective and impactful on the girl-children, there is need for citizen-mobilization, this will bring awareness to parents on the importance of the education of the girl-child and the pessimistic and fatalistic attitudes of people to the girl-child will change. The content of education should therefore be made more relevant to the girl-child so that she will be motivated to learn.

To encourage girl-child education, the following should be embarked upon;

- Existing curriculum should be adapted to suit the needs of the girl-child.
- The media should be employed to inform and instruct on the importance of the girl-child education to the nation.
- The planning of education generally should be focused, realistic and interactive (Adedokun, 1998).

The girl child should be educated so as to help her to compete in the world of men and to give her instrumental skills as well as intellectual development that will help her in making comprehensive judgement about the world around her (Howard, 1991). The educative process involves changes, transition, adaptation and modification and so the education of the girl-child must be rooted in the immediate practical and social life of the girl-child (Howard, 1991).

CONCLUSION

In this paper, an attempt has been made to examine the issues surrounding the girl-child education, the rights of the girl-child, hindrances to girl-child education, the benefits that come to individual girl-child as well as the community/nation through the education of the girl-child. The paper concluded that educating the girl-child eradicates poverty, backwardness, diseases and illnesses in any nation and it promotes personal as well as national development.

RECOMMENDATIONS

In light of the above importance of educating the girl-child, the following recommendations were made:

- Gender balanced curriculum and education policies should be established. Such curriculum must consider the interest of the girl-child so that she is motivated to learn.
- Girl-child hawking should be stopped through public enlightenment and legislation.
- Parents should be educated on the values of modern education to the girl-child.
- Awareness should be made to sensitize people on the fact that an end can only come to poverty cycle through educating the girl-child. The reality is that an uneducated girl that marries early also gives her child in marriage very early; so she becomes a grandmother who eventually has to fend for her grand-children who could not be adequately supported by (her daughter) their mother. Thus, the unmerciful cycle of poverty continues.
- Parents should take advantage of the UBE programme and educate their girl-children.
- Government at all levels, NGOs, media houses should be involved in awareness programme on the education of the girl-child.
- Women should be given the opportunity to formulate and help execute policies especially those relating to girls/women.
- The girl-child should be sensitized as to the importance of her being educated so as to fight for her rights.
- The government at all levels should legislate the rights of the girl-child.

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- The concept of the girl-child should be improved through education. They should be made to see themselves as being capable of doing what the male child is able to do.
- Gender inequalities that leave girl-children with limited educational opportunities should be readdressed.
- Traditional practices that deny girl-children of their rights thereby leaving them poor and forcing them to turn to sex for survival and in the process of which HIV/AIDS is contracted should be addressed.
- Programmes that promote girl-child education should be promoted in all our communities.
- Each educated individual should spread the message of the girl-child education and raise awareness on this issue.

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